

Formation Constant of a Few Alcohols-Carbonyls Complexes

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The dielectric constants of a few alcohols-carbonyls mixtures were measured using a WTW dipolemeter. The formation constants of these systems were calculated by proposing a new method similar to Benesi-Hildebrand method.

As the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonding in a chemical system changes the number, mass, shape and electronic structure of the participants, the measurement of their various physical properties¹⁻⁶ have been studied and the observed singularities in the property-concentration relationship have been used to determine the formation constants of the complexes formed. Though the spectroscopic methods have been developed well and capable of giving valuable information, the non-spectroscopic methods are equally good but only a little attention have been given to it. The dielectric polarizabilities of the liquid mixtures have been used by many investigators^{4,7,8} for calculating the formation constant and not directly from the dielectric constant. Presently an attempt is made to determine the formation constant directly from the dielectric constant measurements of a few alcohols-carbonyls systems.

Experimental

The dielectric constant measurements have been carried out at a frequency of 2 MHz using a WTW dipolemeter DWO1 at the temperature 303°K with a

cell whose accuracy of determination of the dielectric constant is within ± 0.0004 . The chemicals used, the carbontetrachloride, alcohols, ketones and esters were purified by standard procedures. The proton donor alcohol and the acceptors, ketones and esters under study were separately dissolved at the same molar concentration (0.3 m/l) in the solvent carbontetrachloride. Their dielectric constants were measured separately. Then the two solutions were mixed in different proportions but with the total concentration kept at a fixed value and were subjected to the dielectric constant measurements.

Method of calculation of formation constant :

The dielectric constant of the solute dissolved in a nonpolar solvent is in general, proportional to the concentration. In binary mixtures having varying proportions of the solutes but with constant total molarity, the proportionality is found to hold good only if there is no molecular interactions. As the dipolemoment of the hydrogen bonded adducts will differ from that of either of the components and a mixed solution will have a dielectric constant differing from the additive value. In

TABLE 1—THE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF A FEW ALCOHOLS—CARBONYLS SYSTEMS AT DIFFERENT MOLAR RATIOS

Molar Ratio		ϵ observed (Total concentration of the solution is 0.3 m/l)								
A : B		12 : 0	10 : 2	8 : 4	6 : 6	4 : 8	3 : 9	2 : 10	1 : 11	0 : 12
A	B									
Methanol :	Acetone	2.2932	2.3242	2.3541	2.3835	2.4091	2.4219	2.4343	2.4464	2.4581
	Ethyl methyl ketone	2.2930	2.3230	2.3527	2.3833	2.4086	2.4211	2.4334	2.4454	2.4570
	Cyclohexanone	2.2797	2.3251	2.3675	2.4082	2.4449	2.4630	2.4809	2.4984	2.5158
	Ethyl acetate	2.2903	2.2976	2.3043	2.3112	2.3132	2.3140	2.3155	2.3167	2.3178
	Amyl acetate	2.2903	2.2982	2.3064	2.3136	2.3173	2.3183	3.3196	2.3207	2.3215
n-Butanol :	Acetone	2.2909	2.3223	2.3518	2.3800	2.4063	2.4189	2.4313	2.4432	2.4550
	Ethyl methyl ketone	2.2930	2.3238	2.3538	2.3828	2.4092	2.4219	2.4346	2.4469	2.4593
	Ethyl acetate	2.2909	2.2994	2.3054	2.3118	2.3144	2.3153	2.3164	2.3173	2.3180
	Amyl acetate	2.2922	2.3015	2.3088	2.3148	2.3187	2.3200	2.3213	2.3224	2.3233

the absence of the intermolecular interactions as said above, when the total molarity is kept at a constant value and when the proton donor and proton acceptor are in the ratio $R_1 : R_2$, the observed dielectric constant would be

$$\epsilon_{a\bar{a}\bar{a}} = \epsilon_A f_a + \epsilon_B f_b$$

where $f_a = \frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2}$ and $f_b = \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2}$ are the mole fractions of A and B in the above said solution, ϵ_A is the dielectric constant of the solution containing A alone, ϵ_B is the dielectric constant of the solution containing B alone. As the maximum deviation of dielectric constant for all the systems studied (Table 1) occurs at equimolar ratio of the solutes, it is presumed that the deviation is due to the formation of 1:1 complexes alone, and in that case the observed dielectric constant of the solution can be written as,

$$\epsilon_{obs} = \epsilon_A f'_a + \epsilon_B (f_b - f'_a - f'_a) + \epsilon_C (f_a - f'_a) \dots (1)$$

where f'_a is the equilibrium concentration of the proton donor (A), ϵ_C is the dielectric constant of the solution containing the complex alone. Evidently $(f_a - f'_a)$ is the concentration of the complex formed. The formation constant of the 1:1 complex formed is defined as,

$$K = \frac{f_a - f'_a}{f'_a (f_b - f_a - f'_a)} \dots (2)$$

when $f_b \gg f_a$, equation (1) and (2) may be combined to get a Benesi and Hildebrand¹⁰ type of equation with $\epsilon_{a\bar{a}\bar{a}} = \epsilon_A f_a + \epsilon_B f_b$ as

$$\frac{1}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_B)} + \frac{1}{K f_b (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_B)} = \frac{f_a}{(\epsilon_{obs} - \epsilon_{a\bar{a}\bar{a}})} \dots (3)$$

A plot of $f_a/\Delta\epsilon$ where $\Delta\epsilon = (\epsilon_{obs} - \epsilon_{a\bar{a}\bar{a}})$ versus $1/f_b$ should result in a straight line (Figs. 1 and 2). From

Fig. 1. Plot of $\frac{1}{f_b}$ versus $\frac{f_a}{\Delta\epsilon}$ for various methanol-carbonyls systems. 1. Acetone; 2. Methyl ethyl ketone; 3. Cyclohexanone; 4. Ethyl acetate and 5. Amyl acetate.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\frac{1}{f_b}$ versus $\frac{f_a}{\Delta\epsilon}$ for various butanol-carbonyls systems. 1. Acetone; 2. Methyl ethyl ketone; 3. Ethyl acetate and 4. Amyl acetate.

the intercept and slope values of the straight line, the ϵ_C and K values can be determined. Equimolar solutions of A and B are prepared in carbon tetrachloride and are mixed in different mole fractions keeping the total concentration (A + B) constant (in this case 0.3 m/l). Knowing the mole fractions of the components, the concentrations are obtained in moles/litre. In Table 2, the values of $f_a/\Delta\epsilon$ and $1/f_b$ are given for methanol-cyclohexanone systems.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF $\frac{f_a}{\Delta\epsilon}$ VERSUS $\frac{1}{f_b}$ FOR METHANOL-CYCLOHEXANONE SYSTEM

Concentration of B f_b		Concentration of A f_a		$1/f_b$	$\Delta\epsilon \times 10^4$	$f_a/\Delta\epsilon$
In mf	In m/l	In mf	In m/l			
0.9583	0.2875	0.0417	0.0125	3.478	1.2	10.42
0.9167	0.2750	0.0833	0.0250	3.636	2.3	10.87
0.8750	0.2625	0.1250	0.0375	3.810	3.4	11.03
0.8333	0.2500	0.1667	0.0500	4.000	4.4	11.36
0.7917	0.2375	0.2083	0.0625	4.211	5.4	11.57
0.7500	0.2250	0.2500	0.0750	4.444	6.2	12.10

Results and Discussion

The formation constants calculated using the equation (3) for all the systems studied are given in Table 3 along with those calculated using Giles' method⁹. The formation constants determined by the above proposed method for the alcohols-carbonyls complexes are found to be in general agreement with those calculated using Giles' method. It is to be noted that the K values calculated for butanol with all the proton acceptors

TABLE 3—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF A FEW ALCOHOLS—
CARBONYLS SYSTEMS

A	B	ϵ_C	K* in 1/m Present method	K in 1/m Giles' method
Methanol	Acetone	4.9237	2.51	2.68
	Methyl ethyl ketone	4.9423	2.30	2.48
	Cyclohexanone	4.9878	3.09	3.00
	Ethyl acetate	4.7033	3.62	2.10
	Amyl acetate	4.8041	1.88	1.85
n-Butanol	Acetone	4.9587	2.04	2.37
	Methyl ethyl ketone	4.9375	1.79	2.06
	Ethyl acetate	4.7813	1.93	2.00
	Amyl acetate	4.8155	1.76	1.65

* The percentage of error over the calculation of K is about 10%.

studied are found to be less than that for methanol with the same acceptors, which reveals that the proton donating ability of methanol is greater than that of butanol. The K value for methanol acetone is found to be greater than that for methanol-methyl ethyl ketone and lesser than that for methanol-cyclohexanone system. This trend may be attributed to the difference

in electronegativities of the alkyl groups¹¹ which vary in the order methyl > ethyl.

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